

Evaluation of methodology to follow volatile composition over time

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Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the effect of freezing on the aroma profile of cooked Great Northern beans during storage and whether the method to follow volatiles over a long period can be improved by the use of an external control solution. The use of external control solution shall correct instrumental drifts and allow valid quantifications. Therefore, Great Northern beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L., thermally processed, in plastic pouches) were stored at 42 °C for five weeks. The study was conducted as groundwork for a 12 months shelf-life evaluation to observe the flavour evolution of Great Northern beans at different storage conditions. Since the effect of freezing on the volatile composition of Great Northern beans is unknown and could introduce a systematic error, the analysis of the volatile composition was performed both on fresh samples immediately after takeout and on samples taken out and stored frozen until the end of the study. The volatile composition was measured by dynamic headspace sampling combined with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). All samples were analysed together with a solution containing several external standards to monitor and correct for instrumental drift over time. In this study, only two compounds were selected as external standards and belong to different chemical groups found in the sample. Each external standard showed a different response over time. By calculating the relative response factor of each standard, the concentration of the volatiles belonging to the same chemical group was corrected. Most compounds showed higher levels in the frozen samples than fresh. After 14 days, the impact of freezing increased for benzaldehyde and furfural. In terms of long storage experiments, this could have a significant effect on the result. The difference due to freezing could be explained by several hypotheses. The freezing and thawing could induce degradation of pre-formed volatiles or degradation could take place due to oxidation processes. Also, the freezing process and the crystallisation could damage and modify the structure/microstructure and thus facilitate diffusion out of the sample during headspace sampling. Further research is needed to understand the mechanism behind the changes and to gain insight in the effect of freezing on the overall aroma and sensory quality of the beans.

Keywords: flavour, shelf-life, Great Northern bean, time-resolved analysis, accelerated storage

Introduction

Across shelf-life, the quality of a food product can change as a result of various reactions leading to sensory changes with a possibly negative impact on the consumer's food experience [1]. As shelf-life studies can take up to several months or years, it is crucial to standardise and control the instrumental analysis. A time-resolved analysis is often hard to conduct, especially over a long period due to instrumental drifts. A common method is to freeze the samples until the end of the study and analyse them collectively at once, which has many advantages. The analytical conditions are constant and logistics are simple under the assumption that freezing has no effect on the aroma.

Another method is the additional analysis of standards to increase the robustness and validity over time [2]. Internal standards correct individual sampling inaccuracies and instrumental drift and hence constitute quality control of each individual sample. External standards are directed to the instrumental performance as a quality control of the instrument. As a tool to monitor and correct instrumental drifts over time, a control solution containing external standard compounds can be measured with every analysis of the samples. The compounds of the control solution are selected based on the chemical groups present in the samples to be analysed. A variety of compounds gives a more accurate knowledge about the response of the mass spectrometer detector (MS) to each chemical group. It gives control over the sensitivity and allows a more precise quantification for each group. Therefore, the relative response factor (RRF) between the internal and each external standard of the control solution is calculated. The RRF is defined as the ratio between the response factors of two compounds. The response factor of the analysed compound is described as the ratio between its concentration and the response of the detector to the compound. The response is expressed as the peak area and is influenced by variations of the gas chromatography system (GC) and method. To eliminate those variations, the RRF can be used to ensure a precise quantification.

This study concerns Great Northern beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) which belong to the group of pulses, which are high in protein and nutrients with a low environmental footprint [3]. The application possibilities of pulses are diverse, but still restricted by difficulties with off-flavours constituting a barrier to mainstream consumption [4]. The impact of freezing and accelerated storage on the volatile composition of cooked Great Northern beans has

not been investigated in past studies. As groundwork for a 12 months shelf-life study on the flavour evolution of Great Northern beans, the volatile profile of cooked Great Northern beans was followed throughout an accelerated storage in this study. It was investigated if 1) freezing is an appropriate way of stabilizing samples from a shelf-life experiment and if 2) monitoring of volatiles can be improved by adding the analysis of an external control solution.

Material and methods

Samples

Dry Great Northern beans (*Phaseolus Vulgaris L.*) were processed at Greenyard (Bree, Belgium). The dry beans were soaked overnight in water, drained and filled into white plastic pouches. Each pouch was filled with 100 g beans and 150 g water, sealed and heat treated for 20 min at 160 °C. After cooling, pouches were packed and shipped to the University of Copenhagen (Copenhagen, Denmark). Upon arrival, the storage of the samples started at 42 °C for five weeks. Samples were taken out weekly. The analyses were performed on fresh samples immediately after take out and on thawed samples which were stored frozen until the end of the study. The frozen samples were thawed overnight at room temperature. For the analysis, the beans were drained, rinsed and blended with water (1:1).

External control solution

The control solution was measured in triplicates with every GC run of the samples. It contained two compounds as external standard and one internal standard (4-methyl-1-pentanol, 0.12 ppm). The two compounds of the control solution were nonanal (0.048 ppm) and 2-pentylfuran (0.019 ppm) representing aldehydes and furans. The pure compounds were first diluted with dipropylene glycol, and then with water.

The relative response factor (RRF) was calculated for each compound (X) in the control solution by the following equation (c = concentration; Area = peak area; ISTD = internal standard):

$$\text{Relative response factor RRF} = \frac{c_{X,\text{control solution}} * \text{Area}_{\text{ISTD,control solution}}}{c_{\text{ISTD,control solution}} * \text{Area}_{X,\text{control solution}}}$$

The concentration of each volatile compound (A) found in the sample was corrected by the following equation using the RRF of the compound belonging to the same chemical group:

$$c_{\text{compound A}} = \frac{\text{Area}_{\text{compound A,sample}} * c_{\text{ISTD,sample}}}{\text{Area}_{\text{ISTD,sample}}} * \text{RRF}$$

Dynamic headspace GC-MS analysis

The volatile composition was analysed by using GC-MS with dynamic headspace sampling (DHS). The samples were analysed in triplicates. For each measurement, 20 g of the bean blend and 0.5 mL of internal standard (4-methyl-1-pentanol in water, 5ppm) were added to the DHS flask. The volatiles were captured by a trap containing 200 mg Tenax TA. The flask was placed in a water bath at 37 °C. The purge time was 20 min with a nitrogen flow of 200 mL/min and stirring rate of 200 rpm. The trap was dry-purged for 10 min with the same flow. The volatiles were released from the trap through an automated two-stage thermal desorption unit (TurboMatrix 350, Perkin Elmer, Shelton, USA) into the GC-MS system (GC-MS, 7890A GC-system interfaced with a 5975C VL MSD with Triple-Axis detector from Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, California) as described by Alstrup [5].

Data analysis

The peak areas, mass spectra and retention times were extracted from the chromatograms by using PARADISE (University of Copenhagen, Denmark). The software is based on PARAFAC2 modelling. The match factor of NIST databank and the retention index was used to identify the volatile compounds. Statistical analyses were performed with JMP (14.0, SAS).

Results and discussion

External control solution

The relative response factor (RRF) for each compound over time was visualised in a control chart (Figure 1) as a tool to monitor the instrumental performance. Each data point in the graph represents the average RRF of three replicates of the same control solution on the given day (in one GC sequence). The control solutions 'Frozen (1) – (4)' were analysed together with the frozen samples in the same GC sequences. The green centre line (μ_0) represents the average measurement from the first 12 weeks of the experiment. The red lines are the control limits (upper and lower, UCL and LCL) which are +/- three times the standard deviation. The control limits are used as

a tool to monitor the stability of the signal. If a measurement is outside the limits, it indicates a lack of stability [2].

Figure 1: Control chart of nonanal (left) and 2-pentylfuran (right). Control solutions of day 0 – 35 were measured with fresh samples and Frozen (1) – (4) were measured with the frozen samples.

All measurements were within the control limits. Nevertheless, the control charts visualise that the instrumental signal responses change over time and the different external standards do not change in the same way. Based on this observation, the application of the RRF for each chemical group of compounds is necessary to eliminate the instrumental drift.

Application of response factor on selected compounds in sample

The RRF of nonanal and 2-pentylfuran was applied to a selection of aldehydes and furans found in the samples. The changes over time of the concentration of nonanal, benzaldehyde, 2-pentylfuran and furfural in the sample are shown in Figures 2 and 3. The concentrations differ between fresh and frozen samples. Frozen samples show higher levels of benzaldehyde, 2-pentylfuran and furfural, whereas nonanal reaches the highest values in the fresh samples. After 14 days, the difference between the fresh and frozen samples becomes more significant for benzaldehyde and furfural.

Figure 2: Concentration of nonanal (left) and benzaldehyde (right) in fresh (blue) and frozen (red) samples across accelerated storage.

Figure 3: Concentration of 2-pentylfuran (left) and furfural (right) in fresh (blue) and frozen (red) samples across accelerated storage.

Discussion

If the difference between fresh and frozen samples increases over time as shown for benzaldehyde and furfural, it could affect the result of long storage experiments (up to one year) more significantly. Assuming that the correction with the response factors gives accurate results, the levels of benzaldehyde and furfural in the fresh samples did not significantly change over time. Consequently, the freezing process or frozen storage must have affected the volatile concentration of benzaldehyde and furfural in the frozen samples. In other studies about the effect of freezing, the time of the frozen storage played an important role for aroma. Iglesias et al. [6] found that frozen storage of gilthead sea bream fish lead to an increase of volatiles which correlated with oxidation markers. Another study on the aroma of black truffles showed a major change in volatiles, which were identified as possible freezing markers, after 20 and 40 days of frozen storage [7]. Based on those studies, the volatile composition of the bean samples could be affected by the accelerated as well as the frozen storage. In terms of the frozen bean samples, the level of benzaldehyde significantly increased after 14 days of accelerated storage. Those samples were stored frozen for a shorter time than the samples with a lower level of benzaldehyde before day 14. It could be discussed if frozen storage lead to a decrease of benzaldehyde assuming that the level should not change over time as observed in the fresh samples. However, it would still result in a significant difference between fresh and frozen samples. It shows that the two approaches of monitoring volatiles over time could result in different conclusions. Nevertheless, further research is needed to include all important chemical groups in the external standard solution to get a more complete overview.

Conclusion

This study presents an evaluation of two approaches to follow the volatile composition over time. The analysis of an external control solution showed that instrumental signal responses change over time. The change of response is not the same for each analysed compound, so that it is necessary to correct the volatile compounds in the sample by the relative response factor. By comparing the analysis of fresh and frozen samples, it shows that freezing of the samples affects the concentration of selected volatiles. Most compounds showed higher levels in frozen than in fresh samples. To get a more complete overview of the changes and the impact of freezing, all important chemical groups need to be included as external standards. The difference due to freezing could be explained by several hypotheses. The freezing and thawing could induce degradation of pre-formed volatiles and oxidation processes. The freezing process and the crystallisation could damage and modify the structure/microstructure and thus facilitate diffusion out of the sample during headspace sampling. As there is no available literature on the influence of freezing on the aroma of Great Northern beans, further research is needed to comprehend the underlying mechanism of the changes to gain insight in the effect of freezing on the overall aroma and sensory quality of the beans.

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